

Green chemistry : the chemistry of new millenium[†]

Suresh C. Ameta

Department of Chemistry, University College of Science, Sukhadia University, Udaipur-313 002, India

I will like to emphasize on chemical aspects of challenges for environment in the new millenium. The most suitable subject for today seems to me, that one should talk about the newer faces of pollution and the possible methods to be used in combating against multifarious pollution problems which have grabbed this world like an octopus. The other way, I may say that our earth is in a cancerous grip of the air, water, soil and noise pollution.

Environmental pollution is not a new term to all of us. The chemical industries all over the globe release billion tons of chemical wastes to the environment and this release of effluents is increasing day by day. There has been an exponential rise in the amount of waste materials and sometimes it reaches to this extent that disposal of waste materials creates another problem. Although these industries spend a large sum every year for the treatment of waste, controlling the increasing pollution of the environment and also in disposing off these unwanted materials. Even then, there exists a challenge for chemists at all stages of synthesis, manufacture and use of the toxic chemicals where some alternate pathways are worked out or these are replaced by less toxic substances.

We are all aware that the atmospheric pollution in all its facets like air, water, soil, etc. is posing a threat to the living beings in general on this beautiful planet, the earth. Some newer dimensions are regularly added to the kinds of pollution, we are facing. We are going to face another kind of pollution, i.e. polymer pollution because the metal, wood, construction materials, etc. are being rapidly replaced by one or the other kind of the polymer depending on the particular requirement. These polymers are ordinarily recycled for their use in some or the other forms, but ultimately disposal of polymeric goods poses a challenge to the chemists of the day, because these materials do not undergo simple degradations.

Another kind of pollution, which has emerged in last few years is the surfactant or detergent pollution. As it is a well known fact that detergents do not prefer biodegradable

pathways and on the other hand, the chemical degradation of the surfactants will add a new member in the list of existing types of pollution. We have almost forgotten the use of soaps, which are biodegradable and do not create any reasonable pollution problem. Soaps have been almost replaced with detergent powders and cakes for washing purposes, however, we still continue with the use of bathing soaps. The detergent is accumulating in the water resources through domestic effluents. As it is not biodegradable, it may create very many side-effects, if used for drinking purposes.

The human life is based on breathing or respiration, which is nothing but consumption of oxygen. The oxygen so consumed is given back in the form of carbon dioxide. This carbon dioxide is then returned back to the atmosphere in the form of oxygen by the plants and trees through a natural process of photosynthesis. This balance continued for a long, but rapid industrialization, ever-increasing transportation, deforestation, etc. have increased the amount of carbon dioxide in the environment. This increase has caused a rise in atmospheric temperature. Although a number of gases are considered responsible for global warning like CFC, oxides of nitrogen and methane, but the main culprit is still the carbon dioxide. The adverse effect of global warming has been predicted from time to time and these estimates are quite frightening. Therefore, it is of utmost importance to find out methods to revert back to an effective conversion of carbon dioxide to oxygen by some chemical or allied means, otherwise the human life will become miserable in coming decades.

Here the green chemistry enters the scene. The green chemistry focuses its attention on the design, manufacture and uses of chemicals and also the process involved therein, which are technologically and economically viable as well as these do not have any environmental risk. In other word, there should be little, negligible or no pollution potential at all. The principles of green chemistry can be applied to almost every part of chemistry, that includes synthesis of

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molecules with a desired structure and property, catalysis of a process, less polluting reaction conditions, etc. This green chemical approach has been referred by a number of alternate names like atom economy, clean chemistry, eco-friendly chemistry, environmentally benign chemistry and benign by design chemistry.

One thing is certain as far as chemistry is concerned, 'Nothing is benign'. It means that no chemical or a chemical process is harmless. Searching a perfect benign process thus remains an ideal only and it will prove to be a nightmare and therefore, even if one can approach almost a benign process, it is always welcome. So as chemists, we must ask ourselves a relevant question that "Is the chemistry, I am doing is the most benign or I can still reach much closer to a benign process?". There is a movement now towards pursuing chemistry with this knowledge that whatever chemistry we develop, the ultimate consequences of this chemistry do not stop at this stage, we reach our target molecule with a sufficient yield or a particular reagent is very efficient to drive a chemical process, the impacts of this chemistry designed by us will not only be felt by the people involved in it or are going to use this product, but it will also affect the persons, who are not related to it or concerned to chemistry. Synthesizing less hazardous materials in place of highly toxic substances will be just a Hobson choice, until we can provide more benign alternate routes for preparing these molecules or replace these by some other innocuous molecules.

The overall development of green chemistry can be categorized in four basic components : (i) Reactants (starting materials), (ii) Products (target materials), (iii) Reagents and (iv) Conditions of the reaction.

Starting materials used should be environmentally benign. Utilizing biological or agricultural wastes for the purpose of preparing some polymeric materials is a good example of its own kind. Gross polymers have been so designed that they undergo biodegradation in post-consumer use. The deadly poisonous phosgene has been replaced by other harmless or less harmful alternatives in the synthesis of isocyanates, urethanes and polycarbonates. New routes of adipic acid, catechol and hydroquinone have been reported using glucose as a starting material in place of the traditionally used benzene. Since benzene is a carcinogen, a process that would remove it from the synthesis of large volume chemicals in a technically and economically feasible manner is certainly a goal compatible with that of green chemistry.

Regarding the target molecule, there exists a challenge

that one has to reduce the toxicity of a molecule but not at the cost of its efficiency. By blocking the α -position, the use of nitriles to act as a cross-linking agent is retained on one hand while its toxicity is reduced many folds.

Visible light has been used as a benign reagent in the cleavage of a number of oxathiane and dithiane ring systems and also in the synthesis of diazapam and analogous compounds. Dimethylsulfate has been substituted by less hazardous dimethylcarbonate for the purpose of methylation. This dimethylcarbonate is produced by the oxidative decarbonylation of methanol using carbon monoxide.

Use of various organic solvents also poses environmental concern. The green chemistry has focused on the use of supercritical fluids (SCFs) as solvents like carbon dioxide. The SCF solvents are not only low cost and innocuous but tunable to our requirements also.

For all of us, who have taken the responsibility to understand chemistry and practice it as our livelihood either as a researcher or as a production chemist, it is expected from them, that they will be using their capacity in a wise manner. This is most important to note that the chemists cannot enjoy the luxury of ignorance and they cannot turn a Nelson's eye or a blind eye to the adverse effects of the process, which he has developed or going to use for the production of a very much desired or a most demanded chemical. It is important to know how chemists all over the world are putting their innovative ideas and creativity into practice and develop newer synthetic routes, catalysts, reaction conditions, analytical techniques, etc. under the new paradigm of green chemistry.

Plentiful and cheap petroleum has been the dominant starting material for manufacture of most of the chemicals. The present economics favor the use of petrochemicals over biomass chemicals as the cost of biocatalysts is high today, but in the future, biomass will emerge as the only logical alternative feedstock because it is non-toxic and renewable. The use of petroleum has increased due to its abundance, affordability and versatility. Biotechnology encompasses bioremediation, which involves the use of microbes that are genetically engineered to degrade toxic chemical wastes in clean-up operations. Slowly and steadily, biomass is making inroads to niche markets as time is not far off, when use of biomass will almost prohibit the use of petroleum.

The generation of benign alternate synthetic routes is the need of the day and tomorrow. One should not assume that the presently available synthetic routes are the only one possible route and therefore, there is a pressing demand to find newer routes, which create little or no hazardous was-

Ameta : Green chemistry : the chemistry of new millenium

tes. If a compound can be prepared by ten ways in the last step and the same trend is there in earlier steps, then ten-step synthesis will have ten billion alternate routes for the synthesis of this compound. This large number of alternate pathways will not create a problem as one has to select only the best route, which is eco-friendly route. The SYNGEN program is well suited in searching a number of synthetic routes where one may be choosy, which particular pathway is environmentally more benign.

I take this opportunity to appeal all the chemists from all the areas like academia, industries, government bodies and policy makers, who are either involved in fundamental research, development of alternate or less harmful or benign methods, newer and safer applications, chemical education,

management levels and also decision making regarding industrialization, that they should accept these challenges placed before the chemistry community, which are posed by already polluted and further polluting environment in coming millenium and come out with some benign chemistry so as to add a new feather in the cap of the chemists in general. This success will also act as a catalyst in stimulating many more chemists to select this field of study and develop some eco-friendly chemical routes so that the extent of pollution on the earth decreases and the humanity feels relieved of the strong grip of the environmental pollution. So that with pride, we can say –

"Green Chemistry : Green Earth, Clean Chemistry Clean Earth".